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Literacy and Language Education of Adult Refugees and Migrants: Learning Materials and Teaching Practices for LESLLA Learners in the Greek Context

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Abstract

Language education for adult refugees and migrants in the Greek context has been examined through a variety of studies, providing information about educators' and learners' profiles, language courses, and materials. However, there is limited research and few studies regarding the language education of low-literate adult refugees and migrants. In this study, we focus on teaching Greek as a second language (L2) to non-literate and low-literate refugees and migrants in Greece. The paper draws on qualitative data provided by language educators with experience in teaching non-literate and low-literate immigrant and refugee adults through an online survey. The aim is to explore the reported teaching practices and the educational materials that educators use for this specific learning group in the Greek context, shedding light on the insights and classroom experiences of LESLLA educators. The need to teach literacy as a fundamental part of the integration pathway was raised, and interesting techniques and multilingual practices, multiliteracies, and use of the students' plurilingual repertoires were pointed out. This research is firmly rooted in the local context and focuses on Modern Greek as an L2. However, it is a study that could also be applicable to other places welcoming adult migrants and refugees, not only in Greece but especially in Europe, or examined comparatively in contexts where efforts toward the inclusion of low-literate migrants have already been addressed.

Keywords: non-literate adults, low-literate adults, refugees and migrants, language education

Introduction

Adult migrants are characterized by a great diversity of repertoires and educational backgrounds when they begin learning the majority language, and therefore there can be no universal solution to the language programs addressed to them. The objectives of such language programs vary according to the nature of the migration population, for example, refugees, long/medium-term workers or residents, spouses of migrants, newcomers, etc. Other factors in the diversification of needs and expectations in terms of languages stem from migrants' previous experience: the nature of their educational capital, their vocational training, and the composition of their linguistic repertoire. According to Beacco, Little and Hedges (2014), there is a need to account for similarities between the language of origin and the language of the receiving country, and of migration timing, for example, during the phase before migration or on arrival in the receiving society (when the need is urgent), and form of settlement (brief stay, settlement involving regular alternation between countries, long-term settlement, settlement involving a planned return, settlement regarded as permanent, etc.).

To examine language education for adult refugees and migrants in the Greek context, we have to take into consideration three important issues. First of all, classes are highly diverse in terms of language competence, literacy, and language backgrounds of students, in many cases ranging from non-literates without any knowledge of Greek to educated students (Kantzou et al., 2017; Mouti et al., 2022). Moreover, individual students rarely present homogeneous language profiles themselves: for instance, some students who are pre-A1 in writing skills can have oral skills in L2 Greek up to B1, as outlined in the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages: Learning, Teaching, Assessment (CEFR) Companion Volume (Council of Europe, 2020). However, the main issue in the Greek context is that the field of language education provided to migrants and refugees is fragmented, mainly depending on the initiatives taken by individuals, NGOs, or institutions operating on a local level (Kantzou et al., 2017). There is a lack of a more general and unified national-level approach to language teaching of adult refugees and migrants.

As far as L2 Greek language learning opportunities for adult refugees and migrants, there is a variety of different programming options as officially presented on the Ministry of Migration and Asylum website ([Εκπαίδευση | Υπουργείο Μετανάστευσης και Ασύλου migration.gov.gr](https://www.migration.gov.gr)):

- The Migrant Integration Centers (M.I.C.) which operate as branches of Community Centers in municipalities
- Integration Training Centers of Project HELIOS, implemented by the International Organization of Migration. The Integration Centers teach integration courses to those who are registered in project HELIOS, are older than 16 years of age, and are not attending formal public education in Greece.
- Lifelong Learning Centers of the Ministry of Education and Religion provide informal education to adults. In the context of a general education curriculum, the Centers also offer Greek language lessons to migrants.
- Non-governmental organizations and/or other bodies, foreign organizations, and entities representing third-country nationals may also offer lessons in the Greek language as well as informal general education courses for adults. There is also a variety of volunteers offering language support in L2 Greek in various settings across Greece.

As far as formal education is concerned, adult migrants having completed six years of Primary Education and Primary Education but have not completed the first three years of

Secondary Educatory (which are obligatory), may enroll in Second Chance Schools to complete Junior High School education. These schools also provide Greek language courses to migrants and refugees. Migrants aged 15 years or older and unaccompanied minors of this age have the opportunity to be enrolled in Secondary education and Vocational Training in state schools.

Included in the above list of situations are L2 Greek language courses that offer free instruction, although there are also private-owned entities and universities that provide fee-based language learning opportunities. In the majority of these educational settings, non-literate and low-literate¹ adult refugees and migrants may be found in the same L2 language classrooms. In Greece, arrivals of asylum seekers from the Mediterranean route 2022 (12 months) reached 18,780 people (sea and land arrivals). By the first day of October 2023, 30,820 had reached Greece (UNHCR, 2023). The five most common nationalities of sea arrivals (since the beginning of January 2023) in Greece are State of Palestine, Afghanistan, Somalia, Syrian Arab Rep., and Eritrea. There are no official data about the percentage of non and low-literate adult refugees and migrants in Greece. However, in research conducted in Thessaloniki in 2019, around 15% of the refugees had not attended any kind of formal education in their country of origin. Higher percentages of literacy were depicted among Afghans (82%) and Iraqi (80%) refugees, while lower percentages were found for Syrians (68%) and Pakistani (55%) (Joint IDP Profiling Service, 2019). Given the record number of refugees migrating to and resettling in Greece and other European countries, it is pertinent to examine a country's national response and individual institutions' language education offerings to ensure that refugees receive the high-quality education necessary to rebuild their lives.

Language education for adult refugees and migrants in the Greek context has been examined through a variety of studies, providing information about educators' and learners' profiles, language courses and materials, among other factors (egs. Androusou & Iakovou, 2020; Chatzidaki & Tsokalidou 2021; Kantzou et al., 2021; Karava et al, 2021; Kyrlogitsi & Mouti, 2023; Mattheoudakis et al., 2021), but there is quite limited research and studies regarding language education of low-literate adult refugees and migrants (Mouti & Maligkoudi, submitted). This paper aims to explore the reported challenges, teaching practices, and the educational materials educators use for this specific learning group in the Greek context. We aim to uncover and highlight the insights and classroom experiences of LESLLA educators. Drawing on educators' questionnaires, the present paper seeks to investigate educators' experiences in providing language education for non-literate and low-literate adult refugees and migrants.

Research Methodology

This is an exploratory, small-scale study on literacy and second language learning for the linguistic integration of adult refugees and migrants. This study aims to lay the foundation for further research in a field where limited prior research has been undertaken. In the context of the qualitative validation of LASLLIAM descriptors in Greece, we conducted a focus group to fulfill the requirements of validating the LASLLIAM descriptors. *Literacy and Second Language Learning for the Linguistic Integration of Adult Migrants (LASLLIAM)* is a new reference guide of the Council of Europe, developed to support high-quality learning environments for non- and low-literate migrants (Minuz, et al., 2022; Minuz & Kurvers,

¹ We decided to remain consistent with the use of the specific terms as used in the LASLLIAM Reference Guide (p.23). The reader though, could also see, in the 2022 Symposium Proceedings, an article by Nicole Pettitt (2023) entitled "LESLLA defines literacy." This article critically examines the way literacy has been defined or conceptualized in the LESLLA proceedings papers from 2005-2019.

2021)². The validation process, and the discussions it prompted, enabled us to obtain a comprehensive and general understanding of the situation, inspiring us to design a subsequent study. An online questionnaire was developed in Greek, based on the insights from the focus group discussion, and we utilized a random sample from various L2 Greek language educational settings catering to adult refugees and migrants. Data was collected through an open-ended questionnaire, making the approach predominantly qualitative. The questionnaire was electronically distributed and completed by the educators, incorporating 20 open-ended questions. More specifically, the questions analyzed aimed at highlighting educators' profiles, LESLLA learners' literacy profiles, teaching practices and learning materials used in the language education of this special group of non-literate or low-literate adult refugees and migrants. The data underwent qualitative content analysis, (cf. Zapata-Barrero & Yalaz, 2022 regarding qualitative methods in migration research), with the categories explored and highlighted in this paper focusing on educators' insights and practices employed in L2 Greek language classrooms for non-literate or low-literate adult refugees and migrants.

Twenty-six (26) educators answered the questionnaire. The majority of them were women (74%). The sample included educators of varying age: 20-30 years old (7), 30-40 years old (6), 40-50 years old (5), and older than 50 (8). All educators had taught adult migrant learners, with an average of 4.9 years of experience. Regarding teaching experience with LESLLA learners, educators (83%) reported 1 to 6 years of experience, with an average of 2.8 years. The majority had specialized training in teaching LESLLA (23/26 educators). They were all plurilingual with Greek as an L1 and English as an L2. Other languages reported were French (9), German (9), Italian (9), Spanish (8), Swedish (2) but also Portuguese, Dutch, Arabic (4), Persian and Romani. Most educators were either trilingual (8) or tetralingual (8). There was a minority of 3 participants that they said they know their L1-Greek and one other L2-English, while there are other eight (8) cases reporting 5 and more languages. Their bachelor's degrees were mainly those of Language and Literature Studies, and Primary Education departments, although two educators had graduated with degrees in Social Anthropology and Sociology. Moreover, most participants (88%) held a postgraduate diploma or were pursuing post-graduate studies from Greek or Cypriot universities in the fields of Language Education for Refugees and Migrants, Greek as L2, Special Education, Educational Management, and Teaching Methodology.

Regarding students' profiles, their instructors reported that the majority of them spoke a variety of languages, such as Arabic, Farsi, Urdu, Punjabi, Persian, English, French, among others, and that the students mainly came from Afghanistan, Pakistan, Egypt, Syria, Somalia, and other African countries. The majority of their students have lived in Greece had a few months up to four years. The male students in Greece were usually unemployed or manual labor workers (laborers), and women were mainly housewives. There were also school-aged students (aged 15+) with low literacy skills.

Results

Learning Materials and Teaching Practices

This study's results complement our work on the literacy profiles of non-literate and low-literate adult refugees and migrants (Mouti & Maligkoudi, forthcoming). In Mouti & Maligkoudi (forthcoming), we have examined the plurilingual repertoires of LESLLA learners in the Greek context (summarized above) and learner literacy profiles based on the Council of Europe CEFR framework were presented, making LESLLA learners and their stories visible. In the same paper, we recognized challenges and difficulties through a

² <https://www.coe.int/en/web/lang-migrants>

reflection process with the focal educators, increasing their awareness of the challenges L2 low literate or non-literate learners may face in the teaching process. In this paper, we will be focusing on the educators' reported practices and the learning materials utilized in the language classroom. The online questionnaire predominantly included open-ended questions, which encouraged participants to provide more extensive insights into their teaching and classroom experiences. To be more specific, we will present our findings by categorizing them into the following themes: Learning materials, Multilingualism, and Teaching practices.

Learning Materials

Educators reported using a variety of learning materials, as there is no specific material or coursebook especially designed for this specific group of adult migrants. In many cases, educators utilized materials specially designed for young L2 learners, like a multilingual book, *Valitsaki* (Papastathopoulos et al., 2017³) for refugee children aged 6 to 12 whose mother tongue was either Arabic or Farsi or *Geia sas* (Vassou et al., 2007). The Unicef Toolkit of Activities for Multilingual and Social Emotional Empowerment, "*Ftou kai Vgaino*," was also among the tools and materials reported, by using the inclusive activities and tasks suggested for low-literate learners' integration into the heterogenous classroom. *Akelius* the e-learning platform used mainly as a digital language course for supporting refugee children in schools, was positively commented on. For the materials specially designed for adult migrants, the ones reported were a coursebook *Enkheiridio ekmathisis tis ellinikis glossas se metanastes kai prospighes* [*Greek Language Coursebook for Migrants and Refugees*] published by Katalipsi Sinialo (2012), addressing mainly adult refugees; *Gefyres* (Simopoulos, 2016), a bilingual support tool for adult refugees, asylum seekers, and migrants; a multilingual guide *ENTAXEI* by METADRASI (n.d.) and also some other commercially available coursebooks. Although in all the cases we investigated, educators mentioned that, alongside the coursebook, they employed their tailor-made materials for their students, there were also instances where educators did not utilize any specific L2 teaching materials but instead they designed and implemented materials customized to meet their students' needs. These ad-hoc learning materials included authentic samples of learner language accompanied by a wide range of pictures, videos, real-life objects (realia), and visual aids. Initially, these materials were used by the focal educators to help learners build confidence in their oral skills before progressing to writing skills. Educators mentioned using a specific sequence of activities with these ad-hoc prepared materials, starting with a picture/photograph, then a word presented in syllables and spelling format, then the entire words for recognition and copying activities.

There were cases in which mediators were available to facilitate meaning, encouraging the use of translanguaging techniques (Rodrick Beiler & Dewilde, 2023), and code-switching from one language to another as valuable tools inside the language classroom. When no mediators were available, educators encouraged students to translate into their native languages (L1) using their smartphones and applications like WhatsApp. Peer scaffolding and peer tutoring were techniques mentioned in various formats, transforming students and peers into powerful resources for learning.

Multilingualism - Use of L1s

The educators reported implementing various teaching practices for teaching Greek as an L2 to non- or non-literate adult refugees and migrants. First of all, the majority of the educators underlined the importance of their students' L1s use in the teaching process. In

³ All learning materials are included in the appendix of this paper.

particular, they tend to utilize students who are more advanced in Greek as interpreters for students who do not possess a high language proficiency in Greek:

I had a lot of students from Albania and because we did not have one language in common, I used other students from Albania as interpreters. (E8)

[Είχα αρκετούς μαθητές από την Αλβανία, οπότε λόγω μη κάποιας κοινής γλώσσας, χρησιμοποιούσα άλλους μαθητές από την Αλβανία ως διερμηνείς]⁴.

Moreover, the educators themselves frequently use English or French, especially for students who come from African countries where English or French is one of the dominant languages. Among the most commonly reported languages were Arabic, Albanian, Lingala, and Urdu, and educators described their attempts to understand words and language forms of these languages to support their students' meaning making. Educators reported that using more than one language in the L2 classroom helps the students to elaborate more across languages and different writing systems. Thus, promoting and adopting a plurilingual environment in class is one of the basic priorities of the focal educators, as illustrated in these quotations:

It is essential to exploit plurilingualism for the whole student community. Learners of a migrant or refugee background are encouraged to actively participate in the school's activities and to combine their languages. We play multilingual games in class or we read multilingual books. Languages present are mainly Arabic, English, Armenian, Albanian, and Greek. (E4)

[Είναι αναγκαία η διδακτική αξιοποίηση της πολυγλωσσίας των μαθητών για το σύνολο της μαθητικής κοινότητας. Οι μαθητές προσφυγικής ή μεταναστευτικής βιογραφίας ενθαρρύνονται για ενεργό συμμετοχή στις δραστηριότητες και ενισχύονται οι συνάψεις και συσχετίσεις μεταξύ των δύο γλωσσών. Παίζουμε πολύγλωσσα παιχνίδια και διαβάζουμε πολύγλωσσα βιβλία. Οι παρούσες γλώσσες είναι κυρίως τα αραβικά, αγγλικά, αρμένικα, αλβανικά και ελληνικά.]

I often ask for the meaning in the languages that I do not know, so that I can understand their way of thinking and try to explain similarities and differences with the target language. (E9).

[Πολλές φορές ρωτάω το νόημα στις γλώσσες που δεν γνωρίζω προκειμένου να καταλάβω τη λογική τους και με αυτόν τον τρόπο να μπορώ να εξηγήσω τις ομοιότητες και τις διαφορές με τη γλώσσα στόχο].

Teaching Practices

Others reported teaching practices included collaborative learning and differentiated instruction. More specifically, the educators reported that they encourage more experienced learners to help less experienced students when they all work in groups; educators also try to differentiate their teaching practices and aims according to their students' individual needs.

I promote the conduction of projects, based on my students' interests and aptitudes. In this way, language education is more free and in the context of a pleasant team task. (E17)

⁴ In brackets we have put the exact words of participants in Greek.

[Προτείνω την υλοποίηση ενός σχεδίου εργασίας (project) αναφορικά με τα ενδιαφέροντα και τις κλίσεις των μαθητών, μέσα από το οποίο η γλωσσική εκμάθηση θα προκύπτει αβίαστα και ως παρεπόμενο μιας ευχάριστης ομαδικής δραστηριότητας].

Interestingly, the majority of educators (20/26) have identified the diversity of literacy levels in their classrooms as a challenge (E12), along with the need for many repetitions and extra time (E7). However, other educators (E6) indicated that they actively seek out this diversity to facilitate constructive peer scaffolding. These perspectives were not found to vary based on educators' experience or training, while the context and the degree of diversity in each working group could be considered as an important variable.

Since low-literate students coexisted with literate ones, the "challenge" was their parallel support within a multi-leveled working group. (E12)

[Επειδή οι αναλφάβητοι μαθητές συνυπήρχαν με εγγράμματους η "πρόκληση" ήταν η παράλληλη στήριξή τους μέσα σε ένα πολυμελές τμήμα.]

I prefer the classes to be differentiated in terms of literacy - so students of different levels get mixed up and help each other. (E6)

[Οι τάξεις προτιμώ να είναι διαφοροποιημένες ως προς τον γραμματισμό-έτσι μαθητές διαφορετικών επιπέδων αλληλοβοηθούνται.]

Educators seem to adopt several routines in the educational procedure, such as encouraging daily practices such as asking their students to write their names, fill in the time calendar, or ask about the daily number of students who are present in class. Students are also encouraged to engage daily in short dialogues in class. During the first lessons, emphasis is given on activities that promote phonemic awareness and sound-symbol correspondences of the Greek alphabet. The aim is to provide students with visual cues which help them access word meaning, especially if they face difficulties reading their written translations in the L1.

Regarding educators' language aims and teaching techniques for their non-literate or low-literate adult students, the majority of them reported utilizing visual material from students' everyday lives to familiarize themselves with the Greek alphabet. For instance, one teacher (E2) comments:

We focus on oral speech, making them feel more comfortable with the target language. We then recognize letters on signs, labels, tags, etc. (E2)

[Επικεντρωνόμαστε στον προφορικό λόγο αρχικά που τους είναι πιο γνώριμος για να νιώσουν οικεία και με τη γλώσσα στόχο. Έπειτα, αναγνωρίζουμε τα γράμματα μέσα από εικόνες από ταμπέλες, ετικέτες, σήματα...]

Apart from the visual material, the focal educators reported trying to face the students' difficulties with reading and writing by engaging in basic language teaching techniques that involve recognizing letters, correspondence of letters and sounds, copying letters and words, structuring and deconstructing words:

We do a lot of exercises in which we recognize letters, connect sounds with a letter or a syllable, create dictate, deconstruct, and reconstruct words, phrases and match letters or words with pictures. (E4)

[Κάνουμε πολλές ασκήσεις αναγνώρισης γραμμάτων, συσχετίσης ήχου και γράμματος ή συλλαβής, αντιγραφής, ανάγνωσης, υπαγόρευσης, αποδόμησης και επανασύνθεσης λέξεων και αργότερα φράσεων, αντιστοίχισης με εικόνες]

Students' empowerment

An emphasis is placed on students' empowerment, according to our participants' responses. The participants noted that LESLLA students need constant encouragement and motivation to continue to participate in classes despite the great challenges they may face, especially with the development of their literacy skills:

During my lessons, I give priority to the empowerment of my students. My expectations and aims ought to be clear in every step. My basic concern is to help them to reacquire their autonomy. (E6)

[Στα μαθήματά μου δίνω έμφαση στην ενδυνάμωση των μαθητών. Επίσης οι προσδοκίες και οι στόχοι οφείλουν να είναι ξεκάθαροι σε κάθε βήμα. Το πλέον βασικό μου μέλημα είναι να τους βοηθήσω να επανακτήσουν την αυτονομία τους.]

To support students' empowerment, students are encouraged to engage in a variety of oral tasks and exercises (i.e. short and everyday dialogues) closely related to their everyday needs and real life:

My students are involved in short and everyday dialogues during our lessons. I believe that this has given them self-esteem, the fact that they manage to talk, despite the difficulties they continue to have in written speech. (E10)

[Οι μαθητές/τριες της τάξης, εμπλέκονται συχνά σε σύντομους και καθημερινούς διαλόγους. Αυτό, κατά τη γνώμη μου, τους έχει δώσει αυτοπεποίθηση που κατορθώνουν και μιλήσουν, παρόλο που συνεχίζουν να έχουν δυσκολία στον γραπτό λόγο].

I try so that all the activities have a connection with their daily life or with their life in general (E6) [Όλες οι δραστηριότητες προσπαθώ να έχουν σύνδεση με την καθημερινότητά τους ή με την ζωή τους γενικότερα.]

Other techniques were also reported like peer-tutoring and identity texts referring to learners' texts on self-selected topics that may have multiple forms written, spoken, visual, etc. (see Gogonas & Gatsi (2021) for their use in the Greek context), bringing the learners "on stage".

I encourage them to teach me their language (Lingala, Arabic). I believe they have fun and it provides psychological support (E23).

[Τους παρακινώ να με διδάσκουν τη γλώσσα τους (λινγκάλα, αραβικά). Πιστεύω πως το διασκεδάζουν και παρέχεται ψυχολογική ενίσχυση.]

One of my favorite techniques for the first contact and empowerment of my refugee and migrant students is the application of identity texts [...] Students unlock themselves, while they share their personal information and experiences, using their languages, while at the same time, the educator receives information about the students' emotional and cognitive needs. (E11)

[Μια αγαπημένη μου τεχνική για την πρώτη επαφή, γνωριμία και ενίσχυση των προσφύγων/ μεταναστών μαθητών μου είναι η εφαρμογή των Κειμένων Ταυτότητας (Identity Texts)... Οι μαθητές "ξεκλειδώνονται" και μοιράζονται προσωπικές πληροφορίες και εμπειρίες, χρησιμοποιώντας τις γλώσσες τους, ενώ παράλληλα, ο εκπαιδευτικός λαμβάνει πληροφορίες για τις ψυχοσυναισθηματικές και γνωστικές ανάγκες του μαθητή].

Finally, concerning language assessment practices, it appears that oral skills were more frequently assessed, as, in many cases, written skills have not yet been acquired. Oral Reception, Production, and Interaction were primarily assessed, followed by some basic Written Reception. Written Production was not mentioned in any of the responses. Alternative assessment practices have been reported, including class observation, portfolios, and projects. There were also references to multilingual and multimodal assessments in the educators' responses, such as using the native language (L1) in the instructions or incorporating videos, although note that the questionnaire did not specifically ask about assessment practices.

Discussion

What is new about this present paper is the focus on the teaching techniques and practices, as well as the learning materials, in the LESLLA learners' classrooms in the Greek context. This is extremely important as in the majority of cases in Greece, LESLLA learners are found in heterogeneous and highly diverse classes where students with different literacy profiles are found together. This observation seems to be shared in diverse regions of the world in international research databases and in the LESLLA Proceedings (e.g., d'Agostino et al., 2018; Mocciaro, 2021; Gonzalves, 2023; Rodrick Beiler & Dewilde, 2023). The need to teach literacy as a fundamental part of the integration pathway was raised and interesting techniques and multilingual practices, multiliteracies, and use of the students' plurilingual repertoires were pointed out. The importance of teaching literacy as an essential component of the integration pathway was emphasized, and intriguing techniques and multilingual practices, multiliteracies, and the utilization of students' plurilingual repertoires were highlighted. The majority of educators stressed the significance of their students' native languages (L1s) in the teaching process, and they reported extensive use of other bridging languages, such as English or French. Other techniques and practices, including peer scaffolding, peer tutoring, projects, identity texts, collaborative learning, differentiated instruction, and certainly, the use of multimodal inputs, were also documented.

Moreover, one has to bear in mind that Greek is a language that is typologically distant from most languages. In practical terms, its writing system, even if it is alphabetical, is different from the Latin or Cyrillic alphabets, and, thus, literacy in a non-alphabetical L1 or knowledge of another alphabetical system (e.g., Latin for English or other European languages), may not necessarily be an asset when learning Greek. Therefore, the needs of low-literate migrants learning Greek will also vary depending on whether their L1 has a logographic writing system or even an alphabetic writing system different from Greek. This is the case for refugees who can read and write in a script different from that used in the target language. In this scenario, learners have to acquire a new writing system, but they can use their existing literacy skills in other scripts to assist them in this process.

The present study was conducted before the LASLLIAM Reference Guide launch (Minuz & Kurves, 2021), which aspires to be a rather useful tool in the hands of both experienced and inexperienced educators working with LESLLA learners. Certainly, learning materials and assessment tools for L2 Greek designed and constructed for non and low-literate migrants are needed, as “non-literate or low-literate migrants have specific educational needs, as they must learn a second language while either learning to read and write for the first time or developing basic literacy competences in an alphabet or writing system sometimes different from the one they will have learned initially” (Council of Europe. (n.d.). These needs do not seem to be taken into consideration in the existing L2 Greek learning materials, assessment tools, and language course design. New L2 Greek learning materials, language courses, and assessment tools should be provided, based on the

LASLLIAM Reference Guide and thus based on the educational, literacy, and language needs of non-literate and low-literate migrants learning Greek as a second language.

Towards this direction, Mouti & Maligkoudi (2022) worked on the Piloting of LASLLIAM in Greek through the design of sample materials and tools based on its philosophy, scales, and descriptors. Additionally, ALTE (Association of Language Testers in Europe) LAMI (Language Assessment for Migration and Integration) Special Interest Group & Council of Europe (2023) have already provided sample assessment tool based on LASLLIAM, and a multilingual version in different languages (including L2 Greek) is expected in 2023. Certainly, it would be interesting for further research to examine the LASLLIAM implementation and Literacy and Second Language Learning for the Linguistic Integration of Adult Refugees and Migrants in the Greek context through the voices of the learners themselves.

Conclusion

In this paper, we have presented an exploratory, small-scale primary research study on literacy and second language learning for the linguistic integration of adult migrants in Greece. To our knowledge, this is among the first studies to examine the field of low-literate adult refugees and migrants in the Greek context. The LASLLIAM Reference Guide (Minuz et al., 2022) served as the initial point of departure for our study. A paramount facet of this paper pertains to presenting the LESLLA Greek context before the LASLLIAM Reference Guide and our further efforts culminated in developing sample materials that draw upon this study's findings and LASLLIAM Reference Guide (Mouti & Maligkoudi, 2022). Certainly, there are limitations, such as the small number of participants, but it was the focused nature of our population and sample that required prior experience with low-literate refugees and migrants to make it as representative as possible of the LESLLA educators' population. This research is firmly rooted in the local context and focuses on Modern Greek as an L2. However, it is a study that could also be applicable to other places welcoming adult migrants and refugees, not only in Greece but especially in Europe (as discussed by Carlsen et al., 2023) or examined comparatively in contexts where efforts toward the inclusion of low-literate migrants have already been addressed (as discussed by Rocca et al., 2017).

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Appendix: List of Learning Materials Compiled from Teacher Questionnaire Responses

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